

Firefighting robots should be made responsibly

To the Editor– Firefighting robots have the potential to transform emergency response by operating in hazardous environments that pose extreme risks to firefighters. These so-called "firebots" can withstand extreme heat, smoke, and structural instability without fatigue. However, experienced firefighters rely on intuition, teamwork, and years of practice to navigate these dangers. Skepticism toward innovation in high-stakes environments is expected, and if poorly integrated, firebots could hinder rather than enhance safety. To ensure firebots complement rather than disrupt life-saving operations, we argue for a responsible design framework that aligns their development with firefighter values and decision-making processes.

Firefighting is an extremely hazardous profession, exposing firefighters to intense heat, toxic smoke, and the risk of structural collapse. Operating in low-visibility conditions, they must make split-second decisions with limited information while enduring severe physical and psychological stress. These challenges not only increase the immediate risk of injury or death but also contribute to long-term health consequences, such as cancer (<https://www.iarc.who.int/news-events/iarc-monographs-volume-132-occupational-exposure-as-a-firefighter/>). Recognizing these risks, fire departments have long explored technology to enhance safety and efficiency. Teleoperated firefighting robots, for instance, are increasingly used to provide situational awareness and execute basic tasks like towing and fire suppression. However, they require substantial human oversight, diverting attention from critical life-saving actions. As a result, there is growing interest in advancing robotic autonomy to enable a more seamless human-robot collaboration, where AI does not merely assist but also provides decision-making support in high-risk environments. However, increased autonomy introduces new risks, particularly if firebots fail in unpredictable, life-threatening conditions without robust safety mechanisms and oversight.

Acknowledging the risks autonomous systems can pose to society, the European Union (EU) has enacted the AI Act to regulate AI systems based on different risk levels (Custers & Fosch-Villaronga, 2022). Firefighting robots, especially those with autonomous decision-making capabilities, could be classified as "high-risk" due to their potential impact on safety and human rights. Under the AI Act, such systems must undergo rigorous pre-deployment assessments, including data quality verification, transparency measures, and human oversight mechanisms. For firebots, this means ensuring that autonomy remains within legal boundaries, particularly in life-or-death situations. The AI Act also mandates continuous monitoring of AI systems post-deployment to detect errors, biases, or malfunctions.

While compliance with the AI Act could offer fire departments a standardized framework for responsible deployment, it lacks specificity in addressing the unique operational challenges of firebots. This misalignment forces fire departments to make difficult choices: Should they invest in robotic systems despite the absence of formal oversight or delay adoption until clear policies emerge? These conversations happen in resource-constrained fire departments lacking access to standardized firebots due to their high costs, often reaching hundreds of thousands of euros (Schneider & Wildermuth, 2017). Consequently, some departments build their own improvised robots—often referred to in Dutch as "houtje-touwtje" systems ("wood-and-rope" constructions). While these DIY solutions showcase creativity, they frequently fail to meet regulatory safety standards, raising legal liability concerns in case of failure (Verhagen, Neerincx & Tielman, 2024). Beyond liability, the lack of structured procurement and development channels prevents knowledge-sharing and standardization, further complicating firebot deployment across regions. Public-private partnerships and joint procurement initiatives could reduce costs while ensuring firebots meet technical and regulatory standards. However, fire departments must navigate these challenges independently without dedicated funding and policy support.

Another pressing issue is data privacy. Reconnaissance firebots collect vast amounts of data, including images of fire scenes and individuals, raising concerns about ownership, privacy, and compliance with regulations like the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Firefighters have voiced concerns that operational data could be accessed by companies with questionable human rights records (e.g., HikVision), leading to scrutiny from public agencies regarding potential privacy violations (<https://ipvm.com/reports/noway-ethics-hik>). Others worry that such data could be accessed under government transparency laws, such as the Dutch Wet Open Overheid (<https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0046226/>). While legal safeguards often limit public disclosure of sensitive information, these instances underscore the urgent need for more explicit guidelines on balancing privacy with other interests.

Given firefighters' extensive expertise in navigating life-threatening environments, they could offer valuable insights to clarify and complement firebot development strategies. However, research on firefighter attitudes toward robotic systems remains scarce, limiting our understanding of their practical needs and expectations (Weidinger, Schlauderer & Overhage, 2018; Alon et al., 2021). This gap in research translates into their perspectives being frequently overlooked in policymaking and design processes, further exacerbating the misalignment between operational needs, trust, and efficiency.

To ensure firebots effectively support firefighters, regulatory measures alone are insufficient. A responsible design holistic approach as in Fig. 1 is required to integrate ethical, legal, and social considerations into the development process (Van Veenstra, Van Zoonen & Heilberger, 2021). Among the most relevant frameworks for achieving this is Value Sensitive Design (VSD), which systematically embeds key values—such as human agency, autonomy, safety, privacy, transparency, and accountability—into technological development (Verhagen, Neerincx & Tielman, 2024). VSD helps determine appropriate levels of human and robot autonomy, for

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instance, a "variable autonomy" approach, in which robots handle non-moral operational tasks but defer critical moral decisions to human operators, offers a balanced solution that preserves accountability while enhancing performance (Methnani et al., 2021).

Figure 1: Holistic Responsible Design Approach for Firebots

However, for VSD to be truly effective, key values cannot be identified and integrated in isolation. To ensure these values align with the realities of firefighting, those on the front lines—firefighters themselves—must be actively involved in this process, not just as end-users but as co-designers. The EU Commission's Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) framework promotes inclusive and sustainable innovation through co-creation, participatory design, and anticipatory reflection on the ethical implications of technology (Owen & Pansera, 2019). Applying these principles to firebot development means going beyond compliance and value embedding. Understanding firefighters' perspectives, operational needs, and expertise

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can help ensure that firebots are technically effective and seamlessly integrated into their workflows. This alignment fosters trust, usability, and long-term adoption, ultimately enhancing safety and performance in high-risk environments. Furthermore, education, training, and knowledge-sharing initiatives are essential to ensure that firebots become trusted allies, empowering firefighters and protecting communities during emergencies.

The successful integration of firebots into firefighting operations requires a comprehensive approach in which policymakers, researchers and developers work together to address regulatory gaps. They should prioritize responsible research, innovation, stakeholder engagement, and implementation. By embedding values, ethical reflection, user perspectives, and trust-building into the design process, firebots can enhance safety and operational effectiveness.

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